

CONTROL OF BLAST-INDUCED SEISMIC ACTION GENERATED BY TECHNOLOGICAL BLASTINGS

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ABSTRACT. This article presents some of the studies on drilling and blasting technologies applied in the Assarel copper mine. The main emphasis is on examining the seismic effects on a particular engineering facility, located on the territory of the mine - CPT-3. The assessment of the blast-induced seismic loading on the structure is based on an analysis of the registered data on the site. Recommendations for the design of blasting parameters are provided.

Keywords: blast-seismic impact, drilling and blasting technologies, blast-induced seismic vibrations, technological blasting

Introduction

The side effects of the explosion are the subject of in-depth theoretical and experimental research. The management of the side effects is especially relevant for open pit mines. The main goal is complete safety for the environment due to:

- the complex (unique) mining and geological conditions of the deposits;
- continuous implementation of new, up-to-date and high-performance extraction technologies, depending on the construction of unique mining facilities;
- the tendency to apply restrictions on the permissible effects on the human body and protected sites in recent years in the world explosive practice (Mitkov, 2010a).

The impact, induced by technological blasts should be predicted, studied and controlled by the blasting engineer as part of the organisation of the working process. The proper implementation of this activity is critical for the technical and economic efficiency of the drilling and blasting (D&B) operations (Mitkov, 2007).

Hence it follows the main goal of technological blasting, exactly the optimisation of the parameters of blasting operations to achieve maximum blasting effect, defined in the mining practice worldwide:

- complete removal of the rock massif within the design contour of the blast field with conditioned grain size distribution of the destroyed material;
- guaranteed protection of the environment from the undesirable (and in some cases harmful) effects of the explosion, to a level that is practically completely safe.

The concept of "side effects" of the explosion, the parameters of which must be managed to a level completely safe for the environment is correctly defined as *blast-induced seismic, air-blast, fly-rocks, toxic fumes*, released during explosive decomposition (Mitkov, 2014b, Shishkov et al., 2019).

The defined term "criterion" expresses the maximum permissible limit values of the side effect, in the display of which its level is still within the safe limits, i.e. where no damages are inflicted on the protected sites (Mitkov, 2009).

The safe limit value for the effects of blast-induced seismic action on the environment is formulated as:

- limitation of relative deformation in the rock massif in the area: outside the borders of the blasting field, respectively in the area of the foundation of the protected structures - buildings, facilities, causing the initiation of plastic deformations;

- restriction of the development of the existing defects and appearance of new ones in the construction of the built structures;

- prevention of its impact on workers in the protected sites, causing mental stress;

- reduction of the risk of damage to highly sensitive equipment located in the protected sites (computers, relay stations, electronic microscopes, etc.).

The accepted criteria for blast-induced seismic effect are the criteria generally accepted in the international blasting practice:

- for protection of the rock massif - *Coefficient of residual deformations* ($\varepsilon = PPV / C$);

- for protection of constructed structures - *Velocity of blast-induced seismic vibrations* - PPV, mm/s;

- for impact on workers - PPV mm/s.

The permissible vibration velocity in accordance with the accepted criteria is the maximum value of blast-induced seismic vibrations (PPV_z, mm/s), shown in the foundations of the protected object - foundation or rock massif, which guarantees prevention of residual deformations in the rock medium, respectively:

- creating conditions for the development of the existing defects (cracks) and the appearance of new ones in the construction (plaster) of the building;

- development of new micro and macro disorders (Mitkov, 2014a).

In accordance with the requirements of the Bulgarian local legislation (Ordinance № RD-02-20-2 for design of buildings and facilities in earthquake areas in force as of 15.03.2012), the determined Guidelines on blast-induced vibrations are adjusted to the seismic coefficient - design ground acceleration ($K_c = 0.27$) concerning the protection of buildings and facilities (Mitkov, 2015).

Research methodology

The detailed studies were performed in a real rock massif with modern specialised equipment:

- earthquake registration equipment, completed according to the methodology of the Geophysical Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (1964 - 1994);

- UVS 1608 - chronological recording device, 8-channel version DIN, Nitro Consult AD, Stockholm - Sweden (1994 - 2008);

- Minimate Plus™ - InstanTel – ISO 9001 - Canada.

Studies to establish the generation and distribution of the blast-induced seismic impact on the environment have been carried out in accordance with the developed methodological approach, accepted in the leading countries, which was adapted for the real mining and technical conditions of sites in the Republic of Bulgaria. (Project 2000-10, Fund "Labour conditions" - MLSP "Update of the regulatory framework for blast-seismic protection").

The open pit mines "Medet", "Assarel" and the quarry "Lyulyakovitsa" were used as a base for monitoring the research of the seismic impact of the blasting operations.

Detailed instrumental surveys have been performed for determination of the dependence, characterising the parameters of the blast-induced seismic impact at the following areas:

- in the generation zone - in the rock medium, next to the borders of the blast field - the working floor;
- in the area of distribution - in the rock massif between the blasting field and the registration point (the protected object).

Graphically, the dependence is expressed in a logarithmic scale on the axes "X" and "Y" "Registered vibration velocity - Adjusted distance" $PPV = f(R \cdot Q^{\wedge}2)$; $PPV = f(R \cdot R^{\wedge}Q^{\wedge}3)$;

The research includes the blasting of:

- charges of a full camouflet action;
- drill-holes with full technological mass of the charge.

The research also includes control measurements to examine the level of vibrations generated during test blasts and technological blasts.

The seismic impact generated by blasting in the different areas of blastability and in the area next to the protected sites has been studied (Mitkov, 2010b, Shishkov, 2019).

The seismic receivers were located in profiles, distributed from the place of generation to the protected object.

The adopted methodological approach was "reduction of the specific consumption (sc. charge concentration) of explosive per linear meter of blasted mine mass" by researching the dependence of the blasting effect on the geometric parameter "spacing between boreholes", as well as studying the relative consumption (sc. specific charge) of explosive for extraction and crushing of tons of mine mass. (q, kg/t). This consumption is subordinated to the geometrical parameters of blasting – maximal burden (sc. average) for the drill-holes of the first row, spacing between the boreholes in the row, burden between the drilling rows.

This was achieved by designing and performing a blasting test in a zone, determined by blastability, while maintaining consistency in:

- the acreage of the blasting field in accordance with the development of the mining works on the defined section;
- diameter of the boreholes;
- energetic parameters of the explosive charge in the drill hole - number of the charges, length of the main and upper charge; length of the intermediate stemming; length of the upper stemming; schedule of commutation of the charges in time and space.

The organisation of the preparation of the blasting field and the implementation of the test blasting was in accordance with the established practice of the copper mine, where the test took place.

The actual parameters of the blasting were determined when loading the boreholes.

After the blasting operations, an expert engineering assessment of the explosive effect was made by viewing the

blasted pile. The grain size distribution of the crushed mine mass (percentage of oversized rock fragments and average piece size) were observed.

The excavation of the material was also carefully monitored. After the digging of the material, repulsion (ejection) of the rock massif was documented at the level of the floor and in the contour of the blasting field.

The quantitative indicators of the test blasting - extraction of mining mass per linear meter of drilling and relative consumption of explosive was determined.

Results of the performed research

To assess the blast-induced seismic impact on the structures of CPT-3, a series of blasting operations were performed and the parameters of the blast-seismic effect in a rock massif in the area of the foundation of the CPT-3 facility were registered (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Registered parameters of blast-induced seismic effect in a rock massif in the area of the foundation of CPT-3 facility

The dependence "reduced distance - registered velocity of blast-induced seismic vibrations" in the rock massif at the base of the foundation and in the reinforced concrete column foundation was derived from the software of the equipment (Fig. 2).

The analysis of the registered velocity of the blast-induced seismic vibrations in the rock medium and in the foundation (Fig. 3), confirms the expected logical dependence for the propagation of the impact on the rock massif in the base of the foundation to the structure.

Fig. 2. Registered parameters of blast-induced seismic effect, registered in the base of the foundation of facility CPT-3

Fig. 3. Registered velocity of blast-induced seismic vibrations in rock massif and in foundation

The level of the blast-induced seismic impact is repeatedly lower than the calculated value of the guideline velocity of blast-induced seismic vibrations for the real acoustic and wave-conducting properties of the rock massif in the zone "Generation - Propagation from the explosive field to the protected facility" (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Seismic action on the foundation

Conclusions

The main conclusion is that the level of impact generated by the technological blasting on the reinforced concrete steps of the column foundation of CPT-3 is completely safe for the integrity of the structure of the facility. It is expedient, the monitoring of the blast-induced seismic impact in the area of the site to continue in order to collect sufficient data on the required reliability.

The results of the research are a base for recommendations for recalculation of the blast-induced seismic parameters of technological blasting for the protection of:

- rock massifs in the non-working and working benches and banks (bench faces);
- structures of built constructions near and inside pits of the open pit mine.

The studies were performed with consistency in the geometric and energetic parameters of the technological blasting in the different zones of blastability to achieve maximum explosive effect and length of the main charge (length limiting overcoming the technological burden and ejection of the deducted designed volume of mine mass) $l = 8,0$ m

For a certain blasting field, the main indicator characterising the rock massif in terms of blastability - relative consumption of explosive was determined.

In case of a change of the physical and-mechanical, acoustic and wave conducting properties and structure of the rock massif, it is necessary to update the D & B technology. The organisation, preparation and execution of technological blasting generate controllable parameters of the side impact of the explosion on the rock massif and the engineering facilities located in the area, to a safety level for the provoked plastic deformations and the human body.

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